

Data Marketplaces in the AI Economy

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Abstract

We envision a set of universal, trustworthy, transparent and user-friendly data market plugins (called UPGAST plugins) for the automation of data sharing and processing agreements between businesses, public administrations and citizens. Our foreseen plugins will enable actors in data spaces to design and deploy data exchange and trading operations guaranteeing (i) automatic negotiation of agreement terms, (ii) dynamic fair pricing, (iii) improved data-asset discovery, (iv) privacy, commercial and administrative confidentiality requirements, (v) low environmental footprint, as well as ensuring compliance with (vi) relevant legislation and (vii) ethical and responsibility guidelines. To achieve these we need to consolidate mature research in the areas of data management, privacy, monetisation, exchange and automated negotiation, considering efficiency for the environment as well as compliance with EU and international initiatives, AI regulations and ethical procedures.

Keywords

Data Marketplaces, Data Privacy, Data Pricing, Data Sharing

1. Introduction

Digital technologies play a pivotal role in maximising the benefits of a data-driven society and a data-based economy but need to be solidly anchored to trustworthy, compliant, privacy-preserving and environmentally sustainable data sharing methods, architectures, and processes. These will enable citizens, businesses, and public administration/organisations to share and manipulate an ever-increasing amount of data, safely and efficiently. There is a worldwide strive to make our society empowered by data, where businesses and the public sector can make better and quicker decisions. Indeed, the European Strategy for Data¹ actively promotes the creation of common European data spaces providing a seamless common digital market of personal and commercial data to facilitate value creation and growth for businesses and organizations.

In this paper we advocate the need, and draw the map of steps, to design and deploy a set of universal plugins for data sharing, monetization and trading platforms that enable actors in common data spaces to collaboratively negotiate, improve and enforce data sharing contracts automatically (e.g. in the spirit of [1, 2, 3, 4] or [5, 6]), providing dynamic fair pricing mechanisms while implementing energy-efficient data exchange, ensuring privacy, confidentiality and legislation compliance and adhering to ethical and responsibility guidelines.

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¹<https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A52020DC0066>

To ensure businesses and administrations alike can maximise the returns from data driven innovation, we need to consider the following challenges:

- Data providers and consumers do not always understand the true value of data and are often unfamiliar with the requirements of data sharing and processing.
- Emerging data platforms and marketplaces lack the interoperability tools to exploit synergies and solve data tasks across users and platforms.
- There is an increasing complexity of drafting, negotiating and enforcing formal contractual agreements specific to privacy, regulation and other custom requirements of data sharing.

To overcome these, organisations need to be pro-active to ensure that the approach of valuing and promoting privacy, trust, and data sovereignty, as well as competition law, is promoted and facilitated. Data, tools and platforms that do not conform to these values are less likely to be used in business. Furthermore, different organisations may have different needs for each dimension of a data transaction, *e.g.*, some organisations may need help pricing of their datasets, while others may need assistance discovering datasets relevant to their business processes. Our solution to these challenges is to develop a set of universal plugins for data marketplaces, each covering one core aspect of a data transaction. Plugins may be used independently, or in combination with one or more existing data marketplaces.

2. The UPCAST approach: Universal plugins for data markets

In the context of a data marketplace, we assume two types of organisations that enter data sharing or trading agreements: customers that want to create a data product or take advantage of a data driven opportunity that requires the design and execution of a data processing workflow, and providers that offer resources in the form of datasets or data operations, *e.g.*, storage, cleaning, analytics, querying, integration, encapsulated as APIs or services [7]. In some data processing scenarios, an organisation can be both a customer and a provider. UPCAST's (see Fig. 1) aim is to provide end-to-end support to the following common scenarios:

Scenario 1: A customer organisation owns and controls some of the datasets that are required for the workflow it wants to implement. To complete the workflow, the customer needs to look

Figure 1: UPCAST Approach

in data marketplaces and find providers of further datasets or data operations. Providers on the other hand, enable the discovery of their resources within a marketplace. The customer discovers resources across marketplaces that match the operational, privacy, pricing, and environmental requirements of their desired workflow (see [5, 6, 8, 9] or [10, 1, 11, 12, 13, 14]). Once relevant resources are identified, customer and providers need to negotiate the usage and pricing conditions of each resource used in the workflow. All parties want to ensure that any privacy, legal, commercial, and administrative constraints are respected during the negotiation and subsequent execution of the workflow in a safe, secure and transparent way.

Scenario 2: A public administration entity owns or controls a set of datasets and would like to integrate them and enable their sharing or exchange in compliance with legal and administrative privacy and confidentiality constraints. They would also like to understand how much their data is worth in the context of a data marketplace, or, if they are to provide their datasets to an interested party, how much they are worth in the context of a particular workflow. The public administration entity is willing to exchange data for other data or services. All processes need to abide to legal, ethical, and environmental frameworks, and be auditable.

Scenario 3: A data marketplace provider wants to enable their data providers to trade data in compliance with legal and administrative privacy and confidentiality constraints. The marketplace also wants interoperability with other marketplaces to enable a wider data space. The marketplace would also like to understand synergies between datasets that they host order to suggest pricing functions and partnership opportunities to their clients.

With UPCAST plugins, customers and providers achieve their goals executing the following:

- Step 1 – Resource and Workflow Description: Providers and customers prepare descriptions of what they offer and what they need, respectively. Provider descriptions can be (i) Specification of technical characteristics including input/output description for data operations, dataset summaries and certificates of quality, environmental footprint or ethical data management, (ii) Usage conditions, that include constraints on privacy, confidentiality, data protection and pricing, among others. Customer descriptions sketch a high-level specification of the desired data processing workflow. They include the datasets and data operations they own, the requirements for datasets and data operations they need, and any additional conditions on the execution of the data processing workflow.
- Step 2 – Agreement: Based on a Data Processing Workflow specification, customer organisations indicate or discover relevant resources. Providers of these resources are invited to a negotiation where all parties reconcile any conflicting conditions to reach a contractual agreement. Resources are integrated and the entire workflow is optimised to satisfy privacy, pricing, environmental and other conditions.
- Step 3 – Monitoring execution: After an agreement is reached, the data processing workflow is executed in a decentralised fashion, in a secure, safe, transparent, and auditable way, via the processes in place in the underlying marketplaces.

UPCAST considers the role of third-party agents ('oracles'), such as human-based agents, to help meet the need for interfacing between legal language and code. The AI assessment enforces best-practices regarding the reliable, fair and transparent use and development of the automated techniques within the UPCAST framework.

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